

What can learning design do?

A case for pedagogy before technology

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Learning designers are often asked to apply technology to learning. But, if we first apply learning theory, then the student experience can be a lot richer.

Is it a designer's job to edit lesson content?

Use the QR code below or go to youtube.com/watch?v=IYh5sNRnIIY to watch the video (Stothers, 2024), then consider the provocation.

Notes and resources:

- Learning theory: [Constructivism](#)
- "How to make it succeed: Give relevant problems that call on pre-existing knowledge while providing generous help."
Adapted from [Map It: The hands-on guide to strategic training design](#)
- This execution shares much in common with active learning as per the [Carl Weiman Science Education Initiative](#). See examples in action:
 - Recommended video: [Inspiring and resolving a lesson](#)
 - [Menu of videos](#) associated with the initiation.

Resources

Constructivism – <https://edtechbooks.org/studentguide/constructivism>

Map it: The hands-on guide to strategic training design – <https://blog.cathy-moore.com/book-map-it/>

Carl Weiman Science Education Initiative – <https://cwsei.ubc.ca/>

Inspiring and resolving a lesson – <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zATnGROyHF&t=34s>

Menu of videos – <https://cwsei.ubc.ca/resources/instructor/demos>

Reference

Stothers, J. (2024). *Learning Design: A case for theory (before technology)*
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IYh5sNRnIY>

About the author

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